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Managerial coaching skills to improve individual performance through empowerment and work engagement at employee of east java regional revenue agency, Indonesia

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to develop a framework conducted by Ribeiro N, Nguyen T, Duarte AP, de Oliveira RT, Faustino C., 2020 [1]. The research was conducted at the East Java Regional Revenue Agency with a population of 140 employees. Saturated samples are used so that all populations are included in the research sample. Data were collected using a questionnaire instrument with a 5-point Likert scale rating. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) using AMOS 24. The results show that managerial coaching skills have a significant effect on individual performance, empowerment and work engagement can affect individual performance, either directly or as a mediation between manager coaching skills and individual performance. This research enriches information/theory regarding the relationship between Managerial Coaching Skills and Individual Performance Improvement through Empowerment and Work Engagement and offers a new approach to the relationship between variables.

Keywords: Empowerment; Individual Performance; Managerial Coaching Skills; Work Engagement

1. Introduction

The development of today's challenging business environment, competitiveness and growing pressure is getting stronger. Organizations must be able to adapt and adapt to changes that occur if they want to survive against the developments and dynamics of an increasingly competitive environment. To deal with this situation, the organization needs human resources who are competitive and have good performance.

Training has come to be a relevant control interest in businesses. coaching helps make people and corporations extra powerful by reaching high quality and significant effects and by way of changing attitudes, behaviors, thoughts or feelings [1]. Most of the research on coaching is greater focused on executive coaching where an outside coach is brought in to an enterprise to educate executives on a way to improve their performance, increase executive behavior and develop their careers. There is still a lack of information available about internal trainers (managers) who function as trainers for their employees, and research on the relationship between manager coaching skills and employee attitudes and behavior is also scant.

Coaching may be understood as a control philosophy that seeks to alternate the connection among managers and employees. Coaching behavior that symbolizes the nice dimensions of management should result in nice overall performance results. Employee commitment and performance as well as organizational success can be greatly influenced by how well managers do in developing their employees. Therefore, corporations more and more anticipate managers to teach their subordinates due to the fact studies has showed a nice correlation among education and worker

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satisfaction, overall performance and success of organizational goals. This end result is an applicable cause why managers want to undertake education as a part of their duties.

In addition to coaching, there are several factors that can affect employee performance, which organizations often ignore, namely empowerment and work engagement. Empowerment is giving authority to personnel to plan, control and make selections at the work they may be accountable for, while not having to get specific authorization from their superiors [2]. Empowerment in an agency affords personnel with widespread possibilities, records, guide and assets to take a lively position in innovation. Mental empowerment gives personnel the motivation and initiative to use their creativity and efforts to generate, develop and implement innovative thoughts [3]. Even as work engagement is the involvement of the person's ego with work. Work engagement refers to a high-quality, enjoyable, work-related state of mind characterized through passion, determination, and absorption [4]. Whilst people are engrossed of their work, they work more difficult, perform higher, and entire their works-related obligations faster [5].

Basically, the performance produced by employees or workers has a close relationship with the pattern of leadership and management systems in an organization. Organizations need to understand what managers should do as coaches in organizations for their employees is important, such as how they have an impact on their subordinates and the capabilities and traits that managers need to possess.

Research conducted by [1] suggests that personnel' perceptions of supervisor education talents stimulate employees' affective dedication to their businesses. Leaders who undertake a managerial coaching fashion can help their subordinates to thrive and build and develop relationships that are built on trust. As a result, employees experience an increase in their positive feelings, work experience and affective commitment. Other results also show that personnel' tremendous perceptions of supervisor training skills can enhance the individual overall performance in their subordinates. The conclusions on this have a look at suggest that the relationship among employees' perceptions of managers' coaching abilities and their personal person performance are mediated through affective dedication. In different words, manager education talents sell affective dedication, which in turn, improves character worker overall performance. In that study, the researcher also revealed several limitations, namely research on manager coaching skills in employees is still rare and allows future research using other mediating variables (e.g. affective well-being, empowerment and work engagement) to analyze the impact of manager coaching skills on employee performance.

The regional revenue agency of east java province is one of the regional apparatus organizations in east java province that is in direct contact with the community in the implementation of public services in the field of regional taxes, has 35 technical implementation units for regional revenue management with 48 shared office one-stop administration system and hundreds of excellent services and supported by 1,270 state civil apparatus consisting of 620 government employees and 650 non-permanent employees with employment agreement spread throughout east java. The regional revenue agency is the regional apparatus organization of east java province that supports the largest regional original income of east java province, which is an average of about 88% of the total regional original income. As a supporter with the largest contribution, this requires high performance on the employees of the regional revenue agency of east java province in an effort to increase the revenue of regional original revenue. Against this background, research on individual performance is still very relevant to be carried out.

Based on the described background, the researcher can formulate problems as follows:

- Do manager coaching skills have a significant effect on individual performance?
- Do manager coaching skills have a significant effect towards empowerment?
- Does empowerment have a significant effect on individual performance?
- Do manager coaching skills have a significant effect to employment engagement?
- Does work engagement have a significant effect on individual performance?

2. Literature Review

In a work setting, the core of a coach's role is to empower employees by promoting independent learning, personal growth, and performance improvement [6]. The concept of coaching applies in various fields of examine which include counselling, organizational and commercial psychology, sports psychology, medical psychology, children and adult education, and management at some stage in the 1980s and 90s, the application of coaching as an idea and set of strategies to control practice increased rapidly [7]. In 1981, the management consulting firm, personnel decisions international was the first to offer a structured and personalized coaching program to help companies promote change and individual development. Combined with coaching and leadership, managerial coaching is defined as an activity that

allows company management to promote learning, encourage self-discovery of what subordinates want to achieve, and guide them to improve performance [8]. Managerial coaching is also defined as corporate management that empowers employees by promoting independent learning, personal growth, and performance improvement [6]. [7] developed a four-dimensional coaching framework that defines this as a set of managerial skills, namely: Maintaining effective and open communication, focusing on the team, judging people on tasks and accepting the ambiguous nature of the work environment to enhance employee development and improve their performance.

According to [9], the definition of empowerment is to provide resources, opportunities, knowledge, and skills to citizens to increase their ability to determine their own future and participate in efforts to influence the life of their group. According to him, the concept of empowerment has a close relationship with two main concepts, namely: the concept of power and the concept of disadvantaged. Jim Ife also identified 6 types of community strengths that can be utilized in their empowerment process. The six strengths are: the ability to make personal choices; the ability to determine their own needs; freedom of expression; institutional capacity; access to economic resources; and freedom in the process of reproduction. While [10] defines empowerment more broadly as an increase in intrinsic task motivation embodied in 4 cognitions that reflect individual orientation to work roles, namely: meaning, namely the value of work goals or objectives, assessed in relation to ideals or standards the individual himself; Competence, namely the individual's belief in his ability to carry out activities involving skills; self-determination, i.e. the ability of the individual to make decisions to initiate and organize actions; Impact, which is the extent to which an individual can influence strategic, administrative or operational outcomes in the workplace.

The concept of work engagement is based on Maslow's theory of motivation which states that individuals will try to fulfil their self-esteem needs by becoming involved in their work. According to [11], work engagement is the involvement of an individual's ego with work. Work engagement is a description of the extent to which a person believes in his current job and how far his work is useful for satisfying his needs. Kanungo explained that Individuals tend to be more involved in certain activities when they are seen as having the potential to satisfy their psychological needs. Work engagement can be influenced by 2 factors [11], namely: situational factors and personal factors. Work engagement is measured using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES), which includes 3 dimensions of work engagement [4]; Spirit, which refers to a high level of energy and resilience, willingness to invest effort, not easy fatigue, and perseverance in the face of adversity; Dedication, which refers to a loss of meaning in one's work, feelings of excitement and pride in one's work, and feeling inspired and challenged by it; Absorption, that is, being completely and joyfully immersed in one's work and finding it difficult to detach oneself from it, so that time passes quickly and one forgets everything around one.

Employee performance is the way of working and the achievement of employees in a company during a certain period. Performance is not only expressed as the result of work, but also the work process takes place. A company that has employees who perform well, it is possible that the company's performance is also good and its targets can be met, so that there is a very close relationship between employee performance and organizational performance. According to Bernardin and Russel in [12] employee performance is influenced by several factors: Quality, namely the level of a process or result of an ideal/appropriate activity to be able to complete the work with the stated goals; Quantity, which is the quantity produced in the form of money value, the number of units or the number of activities that have been completed; Timeliness, related to the punctuality in completing a task, job or activity within the specified time; Cost effectiveness, the use of organizational resources is maximized with a view to achieving the highest target; Need for supervision, namely in practice, employees carry out their work without the need for supervisor assistance or vice versa to avoid mistakes or get the desired results; Interpersonal impact, namely the behavior of employees showing feelings of self-esteem, goodwill and cooperation between co-workers and subordinates.

2.1.1. Conceptual Framework.

The conceptual framework compiled by the author consists of independent and dependent variables and Intervening variables. The independent variable consists of manager's coaching skills and the dependent variable is individual performance, while the intervening variable is empowerment and work engagement. The conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

Source: designed by Authors

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2.2. Hypothesis of Research

From the conceptual framework above, the relationship between the variables to be studied, namely:

- Managers' coaching skills on individual performance.
H1. Manager coaching skills have a significant effect on individual performance [1]; [13]; [14].
- Skills of coaching managers on empowerment.
H2. Manager coaching skills have a significant effect on empowerment [3]; [15].
- Managers' coaching skills for work engagement.
H3. Manager coaching skills have a significant effect on work engagement [4]; [13]; [14].
- Empowerment of individual performance.
H4. Empowerment has a significant effect on individual performance [16]; [17]; [18].
- Work engagement on individual performance.
H5. Work engagement has a significant effect on performance individuals [5]; [17].

3. Material and methods

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research methods. The population used in this study were all employees at the regional revenue agency office of east java province, totaling 140 employees consisting of civil servants (PNS) and non-permanent employees with work agreements (PTT-PK). In this study, researchers used a saturated sampling technique or the number of samples used was the same as the total population (saturated sampling), namely 140 employees.

Definition of operational variables of each variable as following:

3.1. Manager coaching skills

Manager coaching skills are defined as activities that allow management to promote learning, encourage self-discovery to what subordinates want to achieve, and guide them to improve performance [8]. Indicators of Manager coaching skills measured using 3 (three) dimensions [7], namely:

- Effective and open communication.
- Focus on the team.
- Respect others.

3.2. Empowerment

Empowerment is a person's attempt to take personal responsibility for improving or improve ways of getting work done so that can increase contribution in achieving goals organization. Empowerment is measured using 4 (four) indicators of empowerment [10], namely:

- Meaning,
- Competence,
- Self-determination, and
- Impact (influence).

3.3. Work engagement

Work engagement is a state of mind that is related to with jobs that have positive values and are marked with zeal, dedication and absorption or absorption [19]. Work Engagement measured using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) which includes 3 dimensions of Work engagement [4], that is:

- Spirit,
- Dedication, and
- Absorption.

3.4. Individual performance

Individual performance is the result of the work, in quantity and quality, carried out by an employee in the performance of his duties and in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him. The indicators for measuring performance according to Bernardin and Russell in [12] are the following:

- Quality.
- Quantity.
- Timeliness.
- Cost effectiveness.
- Need for supervision.
- Interpersonal impact

The research instrument in this study is a statement based on a Likert scale with 5 (five) scale options with the following format: strongly agree-score 5, agree-score 4, neutral-score 3, disagree-score 2 and strongly disagree agree-score 1.

In this study using an analytical technique called with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) and researchers use AMOS as an analytical tool.

4. Results

4.1. Validity Test

Validity test analysis is done by looking at the probability value of each indicator. If the probability value (P) is less than the 0.05 significance level, the indicator is declared valid to measure the research variables. The results of the validity test are as follows:

Table 1 Result of Validity Test

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Empowerment	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0.205	0.062	3.292	***
Work Engagement	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0.256	0.081	3.165	0.002
Individual Performance	<---	Empowerment	1.222	0.268	4.565	***
Individual Performance	<---	Work Engagement	0.467	0.091	5.153	***
Individual Performance	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0.046	0.055	0.836	0.004
Value	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	1			
Team Focus	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0.737	0.11	6.687	***
Communication	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	1.035	0.097	10.621	***
Competence	<---	Empowerment	1			

Self-Determination	<---	Empowerment	2.575	0.556	4.634	***
Influence	<---	Empowerment	2.516	0.533	4.723	***
Absorption	<---	Work Engagement	1			
Dedication	<---	Work Engagement	1.233	0.192	6.414	***
Spirit	<---	Work Engagement	1.44	0.221	6.517	***
Quality	<---	Individual Performance	1			
Quantity	<---	Individual Performance	1.067	0.092	11.634	***
Punctuality	<---	Individual Performance	0.684	0.093	7.355	***
Effectiveness	<---	Individual Performance	0.797	0.113	7.077	***
Supervision	<---	Individual Performance	0.991	0.099	10.035	***

Source: processed field data with AMOS

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the P value of all indicators is close to 0 (zero). Thus, it can be concluded that each indicator contained in the questionnaire is valid (legitimate) to measure the four variables of this study.

4.2. Reliability Test

The reliability test is performed to determine whether the measuring instrument is reliable or not. A construct or variable is reliable if it provides a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60. The results of the reliability test are as follows:

Table 2 Result of Reliability Test

Variable	Number of Indicator	Cronbach's Alpha	Remark
Manager Coaching Skills (X)	3	0.882	Reliable
Empowerment (Z1)	4	0.872	Reliable
Work Engagement (Z2)	3	0.867	Reliable
Individual Performance (Y)	6	0.900	Reliable

Source: processed field data with AMOS

The table above shows that each of these research variables has a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.600. Thus, it can be concluded that the variables of Manager Coaching Skills (X), Empowerment (Z1), Work Engagement (Z2), and Individual Performance (Y) are reliable.

4.3. Normality Test

Normality test is done by comparing the value of C.R. (Critical Ratio) in the assessment of normality with a critical value of ± 2.58 at the 0.01 level. If the value of C.R. is greater than the critical value, then the distribution of the data is not univariately normal. The test results are as follows:

Table 3 Result of Normality Test

Variable	min	max	skew	C.R.	kurtosis	C.R.
Y6	3.5	5	0.355	1.713	-1.502	-3.627
Y5	3	5	0.051	0.246	-1.127	-2.722
Y4	3	5	0.326	1.575	-0.381	-0.92
Y3	3	5	0.105	0.508	-0.32	-0.772
Y2	3	5	0.274	1.322	-0.161	-0.389

Y1	3	5	0.268	1.294	-0.113	-0.274
Z21	3	5	-0.074	-0.358	-0.47	-1.135
Z22	3	5	-0.065	-0.313	-0.719	-1.736
Z23	1.67	5	-0.287	-1.388	0.639	1.544
Z14	1.5	5	-0.376	-1.817	0.679	1.641
Z13	1	5	-0.861	-4.161	1.969	4.756
Z12	3	5	-0.096	-0.464	-0.572	-1.382
Z11	3	5	0.092	0.443	-0.828	-2.001
X1	3	5	-0.074	-0.359	-0.234	-0.566
X2	2.5	5	-0.221	-1.067	-0.216	-0.521
X3	2.67	5	-0.027	-0.132	0.243	0.586
Multivariate					41.892	10.326

Source: processed field data with AMOS

From the table above, we know that the value of C.R. is 10.326, which means that the research data is not normally distributed. Thus, the SEM estimation uses the bootstrap approach.

4.4. Structural Model Analysis

Structural model analysis serves to ensure that the model fits the data and to test the influence hypothesis between the variables studied. The estimate used in the structural model analysis is the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE). After performing a confirmatory analysis of the indicators that make up the latent variables and verifying the quality of the data, the next analysis is the complete structural equation model. The results of the data processing for this analysis can be seen in the following figures and tables:

Source: processed figure with AMOS

Figure 2 AMOS Research Model

The results of the fit tests of the Chi-Square, CMIN/DF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI models are summarized as follows:

Table 4 The results of goodness of fit measurement model

Index	Cut off Value	Result	Evaluation model
chi – square	As small as possible	394.421	Poor Fit
Probability	≥ 0.05	0.000	Poor Fit
CMIN/ DF	≤ 2.0	4.640	Poor Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.162	Poor Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.756	Poor Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.656	Poor Fit
TLI	≥ 0.95	0.726	Poor Fit
CFI	≥ 0.95	0.779	Poor Fit

Source: processed field data with AMOS

The table above shows that the planned model is poor fit, because after testing the suitability of the probability values, CMIN/ DF, GFI, RMSEA, AGFI, TLI and CFI are less than the expected values. Therefore, the model was then modified following the modification indices. The results of the recommendations from Amos are as follows:

Table 5 Modification Indices

		M.I.	Par Change
e17 <-->	e19	58.792	0.101
e16 <-->	KPM	10.951	0.053
e15 <-->	e16	15.854	0.048
e3 <-->	e16	6.894	0.028
e1 <-->	e11	7.539	-0.017
e1 <-->	e8	4.166	-0.029
e1 <-->	e6	5.217	0.032

Source: processed field data with AMOS

The results of the model suitability test after modification are as follows:

Table 6 Goodness of fit results after indices modification

Index	Cut off Value	Result	Evaluation model
chi – square	As small as possible	80.801	Good Fit
Probability	≥ 0.05	0.055	Good Fit
CMIN/ DF	≤ 2.0	0.073	Good Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.047	Good Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.932	Good Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.869	Marginal Fit
TLI	≥ 0.95	0.977	Good Fit
CFI	≥ 0.95	0.987	Good Fit

Source: processed field data with AMOS

The table over shows that the planned model fits well, because after testing the comity of CMIN/ DF, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, TLI and CFI values, the results are good. thus, it can be concluded that the revision test results are better than the original model.

4.5. Hypothesis Testing Analysis

Verification of this hypothesis is based on processing the research data using SEM analysis, by analyzing the regression values shown in the table (Regression Weights Analysis of Structural Equation Modelling). Testing this hypothesis is to use the Probability value (P Value) as a result of data processing, compared with the implied statistical limit, which is below 0.05. To test the hypothesis regarding reason developed in this exploration model, it's necessary to test the null hypothesis which states that the regression measure between relations is equal to zero via the t- test generally used in regression models. In the SEM output, this causality test is performed by reading the CR (Critical Ratio) value which is identical to the t-test.

4.5.1. Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

After processing the data using SEM, the following are the results of hypothesis testing in this study:

Table 7 Hypothesis testing

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Empowerment	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0,341	0,104	3,263	0,001
Work Engagement	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0,223	0,084	2,658	0,008
Individual Performance	<---	Managerial Coaching Skills	0,392	0,092	4,266	***
Individual Performance	<---	Empowerment	0,577	0,141	4,107	***
Individual Performance	<---	Work Engagement	0,130	0,050	2,589	0.010

Source: processed field data

Hypothesis testing in this study, it appears that the most dominant estimated value is the influence between individual performance on empowerment with an estimate value of 0.577, then followed by the influence between individual performance on manager coaching skills with an estimate value of 0.392, the influence between manager coaching skills on empowerment with an estimate value of 0.341, the effect of work engagement on managers' coaching skills with an estimate value of 0.223, and the influence of individual performance on managers' coaching skills with an estimate value of 0.130.

4.5.1. Indirect Effect Hypothesis Test

In the indirect effect test, a Sobel test will be carried out to ensure there is an indirect effect or mediating effect on the variable interview. The results of the Sobel test are as follows:

Table 8 Sobel Test Results

Path analysis	Sobel Value	P
Manager coaching skills towards individual performance through empowerment	2.599	0.009
Manager coaching skills towards individual performance through work engagement	2.227	0.026

Source: processed field data

Based on the table above, all pathways tested achieved a statistical Sobel test score above 1.96 and a P-value below 0.05. This shows that empowerment and work engagement mediate manager coaching skills related to an individual performance.

5. Discussion

5.1. The Influence of managers' coaching skills on individual performance

The analysis result of the C.R value (critical ratio) for judging the influence of the variable manager's coaching skill on the individual performance 2.589 exceeds the requirement 1.96, and the probability value is 0.01 or less than 0.05. From this we can conclude that the first hypothesis was accepted. In short, manager coaching skills have a positive and significant impact on an individual performance. In short, changes in manager coaching skills have a one-way impact on changes in an individual performance. It will improve the coaching skills of managers, improve individual performance and have a statistically significant impact on employee of the company. These results support the research conducted by [1]; [13]; [14].

The traditional management concept is that managers are responsible for developing their employees. Therefore, the quality of the relationship between superiors and subordinates plays an important role in fostering a positive attitude for employees and achieve future success. Employees who feel valued by the organization will tend to "pay" by increasing their performance.

5.2. The influence of manager coaching skills on empowerment

The result of the C.R (Critical Ratio) value analysis to determine the effect of the manager's coaching skill variable on empowerment is 3.263, which is greater than the requirement 1.96 and the probability value is 0.001 less than 0.05. From this we can conclude that the second hypothesis was accepted, that Manager Coaching Skills have a positive and significant influence on Empowerment, meaning that changes in Manager Coaching Skills have a unidirectional effect on Empowerment changes or in other words if Manager Coaching Skills increase, there will be an increase in Empowerment and statistically has significant influence on employee of the company. These results support the research conducted by [3]; [15].

It is undeniable that empowerment can give employees the motivation and initiative to use their creativity in producing new innovations [3]. For organizations aiming to maximize the potential that exists in their employees, it is important to provide access to the information, resources, support and opportunities that employees need. This is the responsibility of the leadership and management of the organization.

5.3. The influence of manager coaching skills on work engagement

The result of the C.R (Critical Ratio) value analysis to determine the effect of the manager's coaching skill variable on empowerment is 2.658, which is greater than the requirement 1.96 and the probability value is 0.008 less than 0.05. From this we can conclude that the third hypothesis was accepted. In short, manager coaching skills have a significant positive impact on work engagement. Changes in manager coaching skills have a one-way impact on changes in work engagement. Improving manager coaching skills improves work engagement and has a statistically significant impact on employee of the company. These results support the research conducted by [4]; [13]; [14].

Work engagement is identical to employee motivation. Based on the LMX theory, the quality of good leadership and subordinate relationships is characterized by an attitude of mutual support, mutual trust, good and comfortable communication, and loyalty between leaders and subordinates. Such a work environment will increase work motivation and employee engagement in the organization.

5.4. The influence of empowerment on individual performance

The results of the C.R (Critical Ratio) value analysis determine the impact of empowerment variables on individual performance 4.266 is greater than the requirement 1.96 and the probability value is close to zero or less than 0.05. This accepts the fourth hypothesis that empowerment has a positive and significant positive impact on an individual performance. In short, changes in empowerment have a one-way effect on changes in an individual performance. Increased empowerment improves individual performance and has a statistically significant effect to employees of the company. These results support the research conducted by [16]; [17]; [18].

Psychologically empowered employees will motivate and use creativity to produce and develop innovations, or in other words increase employee productivity.

5.5. The influence of work engagement on individual performance

The results of the C.R (Critical Ratio) value analysis determine the impact of work engagement variables on individual performance. This is greater than the requirement 1.96 and the probability value is close to zero or less than 0.05. From this we can conclude that the fifth hypothesis was accepted. In short, work engagement has a positive and significant impact on an individual performance. Changes in work engagement have a one-way impact on changes in individual performance. That is, when work engagement increases will improves personal performance and has a statistically significant impact on employees of the company. These results support the research conducted by [5]; [17].

Employees who have work engagement will have positive thoughts marked by enthusiasm for work, feeling proud of what they are doing, and being happy at work. When employees are engaged, they work harder, perform better and get things done faster.

5.6. The influence of manager coaching skills on individual performance through empowerment

Grounded on the computation results of the Sobel test, the t- count is 2.599 greater than the recommended of 1.96, and the probability value is 0.009 lower than 0.05. We can conclude that empowerment has a mediating effect on the relationship between manager coaching skills and individual performance. In short, changing the value of empowerment has a one-way effect on changing the effectiveness of managers coaching skills on individual performance.

5.7. The influence of manager coaching skills on individual performance through work engagement

Grounded on the results of the Sobel test computation, the t- count value is 2.227 or greater than the recommended of 1.96 and the probability value is 0.026 or lower than 0.05. So it can be concluded that work engagement mediates the relationship between manager coaching skills and individual performance, meaning that changes in the value of work engagement have a direct effect on changes in the influence between manager coaching skills on individual performance or if work engagement increases there will be a significant increase in the level of relationship between manager coaching skills and individual performance on employees of the company.

Based on descriptive analysis, work engagement has the smallest mean value of 4.056, while based on the results of hypothesis testing, work engagement on individual performance has the smallest estimated value of 0.130. This shows that individual employee performance can be improved by optimizing the role of leadership in increasing engagement with the organization.

5.8. Managerial Implication

In addition to providing input for organizations/companies, this research also provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between managerial coaching skills and individual performance improvement through empowerment and work engagement.

6. Conclusion

Grounded on the exploration that has been done, the researchers can formulate the conclusions obtained as follows:

- Manager coaching skills have a significant influence on individual performance.
- Manager coaching skills have a significant influence on empowerment.
- Manager coaching skills have a significant influence on work engagement.
- Empowerment has a significant effect on individual performance.
- Work engagement has a significant effect on individual performance.
- Empowerment and work engagement as mediating variables are able to have a significant influence on managers' coaching skills on individual performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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